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Home Automation and Security System

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ABSTRACT

Easy Home or Home automation plays a very important role in modern era because of its flexibility in using it at different places with high precision which will save money and time by decreasing human hard work. Prime focus of this technology is to control the household equipment's like light, fan, door, AC etc. automatically. This research paper has detailed information on Home Automation and Security System using Arduino, GSM and how we can control home appliances using Android application. Whenever a person will enter into the house then the count of the number of persons entering in the house will be incremented, in Home Automation mode appliances will be turned on whereas in security light will be turned on along with the alarm. The count of the number of persons entering the house is also displayed on the LCD screen. In Home Automation mode when the room will become empty i.e. the count of persons reduces to zero then the appliances will be turned off making the system power efficient. Moreover a person can control his home appliances by using an android application present in his mobile phone which will reduce the human hard work. At the same time if anyone enters while security mode is on a SMS will be sent to house owner's mobile phone which will indicate the presence of a person inside the house. The alarm can be turned of using SMS or Android application.

KEYWORDS

Home Automation, Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM), Short Message Service (SMS), Android Apps.

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- [3] Home Automation and Security System Using Android ADK by Deepali Javale, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Computer Engg, MAEER's MITCOE, Pune, India; Mohd. Mohsin Student Dept. of Computer Engg MAEER's MITCOE Pune, India; Shreerang Nandanwar Student Dept. of Computer Engg MAEER's MITCOE Pune, India; Mayur Shingate Student Dept. of Computer Engg MAEER's MITCOE Pune, India, International Journal of Electronics Communication and Computer Technology (IJECCCT) Volume 3 Issue 2 (March 2013).
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Prediction of lung cancer using image processing techniques: a review

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ABSTRACT

Prediction of lung cancer is most challenging problem due to structure of cancer cell, where most of the cells are overlapped each other. The image processing techniques are mostly used for prediction of lung cancer and also for early detection and treatment to prevent the lung cancer. To predict the lung cancer various features are extracted from the images therefore, pattern recognition based approaches are useful to predict the lung cancer. Here, a comprehensive review for the prediction of lung cancer by previous researcher using image processing techniques is presented. The summary for the prediction of lung cancer by previous researcher using image processing techniques is also presented.

KEYWORDS

Classification, lung cancer, accuracy, image processing techniques.

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A literature survey on recommendation system based on sentiment analysis

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ABSTRACT

Recommender systems have grown to be a critical research subject after the emergence of the first paper on collaborative filtering in the Nineties. Despite the fact that educational studies on recommender systems, has extended extensively over the last 10 years, there are deficiencies in the complete literature evaluation and classification of that research. Because of this, we reviewed articles on recommender structures, and then classified those based on sentiment analysis. The articles are categorized into three techniques of recommender system, i.e.; collaborative filtering (CF), content based and context based. We have tried to find out the research papers related to sentiment analysis based recommender system. To classify research done by authors in this field, we have shown different approaches of recommender system based on sentiment analysis with the help of tables. Our studies give statistics, approximately trends in recommender structures research, and gives practitioners and researchers with perception and destiny route on the recommender system using sentiment analysis. We hope that this paper enables all and sundry who is interested in recommender systems research with insight for destiny.

KEYWORDS

Recommender systems; Literature review, Sentimental analysis

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Text mining: open source tokenization tools – an analysis

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ABSTRACT

Text mining is the process of extracting interesting and non-trivial knowledge or information from unstructured text data. Text mining is the multidisciplinary field which draws on data mining, machine learning, information retrieval, computational linguistics and statistics. Important text mining processes are information extraction, information retrieval, natural language processing, text classification, content analysis and text clustering. All these processes are required to complete the preprocessing step before doing their intended task. Pre-processing significantly reduces the size of the input text documents and the actions involved in this step are sentence boundary determination, natural language specific stop-word elimination, tokenization and stemming. Among this, the most essential and important action is the tokenization. Tokenization helps to divide the textual information into individual words. For performing tokenization process, there are many open source tools are available. The main objective of this work is to analyze the performance of the seven open source tokenization tools. For this comparative analysis, we have taken Nlpdotnet Tokenizer, Mila Tokenizer, NLTK Word Tokenize, TextBlob Word Tokenize, MBSP Word Tokenize, Pattern Word Tokenize and Word Tokenization with Python NLTK. Based on the results, we observed that the Nlpdotnet Tokenizer tool performance is better than other tools.

KEYWORDS

Text Mining, Preprocessing, Tokenization, machine learning, NLP.

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A new decision tree method for data mining in medicine

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ABSTRACT

Today, enormous amount of data is collected in medical databases. These databases may contain valuable information encapsulated in nontrivial relationships among symptoms and diagnoses. Extracting such dependencies from historical data is much easier to done by using medical systems. Such knowledge can be used in future medical decision making. In this paper, a new algorithm based on C4.5 to mind data for medince applications proposed and then it is evaluated against two datasets and C4.5 algorithm in terms of accuracy.

KEYWORDS

Data mining, Medicine, Classification, Decision Tree, ID3, C4.5

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Machine learning systems based on xg Boost and MLP neural network applied in satellite lithium-ion battery sets impedance estimation

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the internal impedance of the lithium-ion battery pack (important measure of the degradation level of the batteries) is estimated by means of machine learning systems based on supervised learning techniques MLP - Multi Layer Perceptron - neural network and xgBoost - Gradient Tree Boosting. Therefore, characteristics of the electric power system, in which the battery pack is inserted, are extracted and used in the construction of supervised models through the application of two different techniques based on Gradient Tree Boosting and Multi Layer Perceptron neural network. Finally, with the application of statistical validation techniques, the accuracy of both models are calculated and used for the comparison between them and the feasibility analysis regarding the use of such models in real systems

KEYWORDS

Lithium-ion battery, Internal impedance, State of charge, Multi Layer Perceptron, Gradient Tree Boosting, xgBoost

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Voice Command System Using Raspberry PI

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research paper is to illustrate the implementation of a Voice Command System. This system works on the primary input of a user's voice. Using voice as an input, we were able to convert it to text using a speech to text engine. The text hence produced was used for query processing and fetching relevant information. When the information was fetched, it was then converted to speech using speech to text conversion and the relevant output to the user was given. Additionally, some extra modules were also implemented which worked on the concept of keyword matching. These included telling time, weather and notification from social applications.

KEYWORDS

Text to speech; Speech to text; Raspberry Pi; Voice Command System; Query Processing

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Fuzzy-based multiple path selection method for improving energy efficiency in bandwidth-efficient cooperative authentications of wsns

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ABSTRACT

In wireless sensor networks, adversaries can easily compromise sensors because the sensor resources are limited. The compromised nodes can inject false data into the network injecting false data attacks. The injecting false data attack has the goal of consuming unnecessary energy in en-route nodes and causing false alarms in a sink. A bandwidth-efficient cooperative authentication scheme detects this attack based on the random graph characteristics of sensor node deployment and a cooperative bit-compressed authentication technique. Although this scheme maintains a high filtering probability and high reliability in the sensor network, it wastes energy in en-route nodes due to a multireport solution. In this paper, our proposed method effectively selects a number of multireports based on the fuzzy rule-based system. We evaluated the performance in terms of the security level and energy savings in the presence of the injecting false data attacks. The experimental results indicate that the proposed method improves the energy efficiency up to 10% while maintaining the same security level as compared to the existing scheme.

KEYWORDS

Wireless sensor network, Network security, bandwidth-efficient cooperative authentication scheme, fuzzy logic

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Hybrid data clustering approach using k-means and flower pollination algorithm

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ABSTRACT

Data clustering is a technique for clustering set of objects into known number of groups. Several approaches are widely applied to data clustering so that objects within the clusters are similar and objects in different clusters are far away from each other. K-Means, is one of the familiar center based clustering algorithms since implementation is very easy and fast convergence. However, K-Means algorithm suffers from initialization, hence trapped in local optima. Flower Pollination Algorithm (FPA) is the global optimization technique, which avoids trapping in local optimum solution. In this paper, a novel hybrid data clustering approach using Flower Pollination Algorithm and K-Means (FPAKM) is proposed. The proposed algorithm results are compared with K-Means and FPA on eight datasets. From the experimental results, FPAKM is better than FPA and K-Means.

KEYWORDS

Cluster Analysis, K-Means, Flower Pollination algorithm, global optimum, swarm intelligence, natureinspired.

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Big data summarization: framework, challenges and possible solutions

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we first briefly review the concept of big data, including its definition, features, and value. We then present background technology for big data summarization brings to us. The objective of this paper is to discuss the big data summarization framework, challenges and possible solutions as well as methods of evaluation for big data summarization. Finally, we conclude the paper with a discussion of open problems and future directions.

KEYWORDS

Big data, Big data summarization, Data Generalization, Semantic term Identification

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